

2-TOM, 1-SON
SOCHILISH NAZARIYASINING TESKARI MASALASI

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Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada sochilish nazariyasining berilganlari orqali $u(x)$ potensialni topish, shu bilan birga sochilish nazariyasining berilganlari orqali $u(x)$ potensialni topish imkonini beradigan asosiy integral tenglama keltirilgan

Kalit so'zlar: xos qiymat, Loran qatori, xos funksiya, sochilish nazariyasining berilganlari, integral tenglama,

Kirish:

Sochilish nazariyasining teskari masalasi deb, sochilish nazariyasining berilganlari orqali $u(x)$ potensialni topishga aytiladi.

$a(\xi)$ ($\text{Im } \xi > 0$) funksiyani $r(\xi) = \frac{b(\xi)}{a(\xi)}$ funksiya va L operatorning ξ_k ($\text{Im } \xi_k > 0$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, N$) xos qiymatlari orqali

$$a(\xi) = \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\ln(1 + |r(\zeta)|^2)}{\zeta - \xi} d\zeta \right\} \prod_{k=1}^n \frac{\xi - \xi_k}{\xi - \bar{\xi}_k}$$

qurish mumkin.

Bu tenglik L operator karrali xos qiymatga ega holda, ushbu

$$a(\xi) = \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\ln(1 + |r(\zeta)|^2)}{\zeta - \xi} d\zeta \right\} \prod_{k=1}^n \left(\frac{\xi - \xi_k}{\xi - \bar{\xi}_k} \right)^{m_k}$$

ko'rinishda bo'ladi.

Endi biz sochilish nazariyasining berilganlari yordamida $u(x)$ potensialni topish imkonini beradigan asosiy integral tenglamani keltirib chiqaramiz.

Buning uchun **Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.** asimptotik formulalarga asosan

$$r(\xi) = \frac{b(\xi)}{a(\xi)} = \underline{O} \left(\frac{1}{|\xi|} \right) \quad (1)$$

asimptotika o'rinni bo'lishini topamiz. Bundan esa $r(\xi) \in L^2(-\infty, \infty)$ bo'lishi kelib chiqadi.

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Shuning uchun ushbu

$$F_1(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} r(\xi) e^{i\xi x} dx$$

Furye almashtirishi mavjud bo'lib, $F_1(x) \in L^2(-\infty, \infty)$ bo'ladi.

Quyidagi

$$S_{11}(\xi) = \frac{1}{a(\xi)} \tag{2}$$

belgilashni kiritamiz. Ravshanki, $S_{11}(\xi)$ funksiya yuqori yarim tekislikka **meromor**f davom qiladi va u yerda $\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_N$ cheklita mos ravishda $m_1, m_2, \dots, m_N$ karrali bo'lgan qutblarga ega bo'ladi. (2) funksiyani $0 < |\xi - \xi_n| < \rho_k$ ($k = 1, 2, \dots, N$) xalqalarda Loran qatoriga yoyamiz:

$$S_{11}(\xi) = (\xi - \xi_k)^{-m_k} S_{m_k}^{(k)} + (\xi - \xi_k)^{-m_k+1} S_{m_k-1}^{(k)} + \dots + (\xi - \xi_k)^{-1} S_1^{(k)} + S_0^{(k)} + \dots ,$$

$$k = 1, 2, \dots, N$$

Xos funksiya va yopishgan funksiyalar aniqlanishiga ko'ra shunday noldan farqli $R_1^{(k)}, R_2^{(k)}, \dots, R_{m_k}^{(k)}$ sonlar mavjud bo'lib, quyidagi munosabatlar o'rinli bo'ladi:

$$\begin{aligned} {}^0\varphi(x, \xi_k) S_{m_k}^{(k)} &= {}^0\psi(x, \xi_k) R_{m_k}^{(k)}, \\ {}^0\varphi(x, \xi_k) S_{m_k-1}^{(k)} + {}^{(1)}\varphi(x, \xi_k) S_{m_k}^{(k)} &= {}^0\psi(x, \xi_k) R_{m_k-1}^{(k)} + {}^{(1)}\psi(x, \xi_k) R_{m_k}^{(k)}, \\ \dots \dots \dots & \\ {}^0\varphi(x, \xi_k) S_1^{(k)} + {}^{(1)}\varphi(x, \xi_k) S_2^{(k)} + \dots + \frac{1}{(m_k-1)!} {}^{(m_k-1)}\varphi(x, \xi_k) S_{m_k}^{(k)} &= \\ = {}^0\psi(x, \xi_k) R_1^{(k)} + {}^{(1)}\psi(x, \xi_k) R_2^{(k)} + \dots + \frac{1}{(m_k-1)!} {}^{(m_k-1)}\psi(x, \xi_k) R_{m_k}^{(k)}, & \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, N \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

$\{r^+(\xi) \equiv \frac{b(\xi)}{a(\xi)}, \xi_k, R_1^{(k)}, R_2^{(k)}, \dots, R_{m_k}^{(k)}, k = 1, 2, \dots, N\}$ tizimga L operatorning

sohilish nazariyasining berilganlari deyiladi. Ravshanki, $R_j^{(k)}$ lar $\{\chi_1^{(k)}, \chi_2^{(k)}, \dots, \chi_{m_k}^{(k)}\}$ ($j = 1, \dots, m_k$) normallovchi sonlar tizimi orqali chiziqli ifodalanadi. Ushbu

$$\begin{cases} \varphi = a(\xi)\bar{\psi} + b(\xi)\psi, \\ \bar{\varphi} = -\bar{a}(\xi)\psi + \bar{b}(\xi)\bar{\psi} \end{cases} \quad \text{tengliklarning birinchi}$$

$\varphi = a(\xi)\bar{\psi} + b(\xi)\psi$
tengligini quyidagi

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$$\frac{1}{a(\xi)}\varphi = \bar{\psi} + r^+(\xi)\psi$$

ko‘rinishda yozib olamiz. Oxirgi tenglikka ψ funksiya uchun

$$\psi(x, \xi) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\xi x} + \int_x^\infty K(x, t) e^{i\xi t} dt \quad \text{Levin tasvirini qo‘yib}$$

$$S_{11}(\xi)\varphi(x, \xi) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{-i\xi x} + \int_x^\infty \bar{K}(x, s) e^{-i\xi s} ds + \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} r^+(\xi) e^{i\xi x} + \int_x^\infty r^+(\xi) K(x, s) e^{i\xi s} ds \quad (4)$$

tenglikni xosil qilamiz. Bu tenglikning ikkala tarafini ham

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{\sin \varepsilon \xi}{\varepsilon \xi} e^{i\xi z} \quad (z > x, \quad 0 < \varepsilon < \frac{z-x}{2})$$

funksiyaga ko‘paytirib ξ bo‘yicha $-\infty$ dan ∞ integrallaymiz va $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ da limitga o‘tamiz. Unda (4) tenglikning o‘ng tarafi quyidagi ko‘rinishda bo‘ladi:

$$RHS = \bar{K}(x, z) + F_1(x+z) \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} + \int_x^\infty K(x, s) F_1(s+z) ds. \quad (5)$$

Bu yerda

$$F_s(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^\infty r^+(\xi) e^{i\xi x} d\xi. \quad (6)$$

Chap tarafi **Jordan** lemmasiga ko‘ra yuqori yarim tekislikda $\varepsilon < \frac{z-x}{2}$ da

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^\infty \frac{\sin \varepsilon \xi}{\varepsilon \xi} \varphi(x, \xi) S_{11}(\xi) e^{i\xi z} d\xi = i \sum_{k=1}^N \operatorname{res}\{\varphi(x, \xi) S_{11}(\xi) e^{i\xi z}\} \quad (7)$$

bo‘ladi. $\varphi(x, \xi) e^{i\xi z}$ funksiyaning ξ_k nuqta atrofida Teylor qatoriga yoyamiz:

$$\varphi(x, \xi) e^{i\xi z} = \sum_{j=0}^{m_k-1} \frac{(\xi - \xi_k)^j}{j!} \left\{ \sum_{l=0}^j C_j^{(j-l)} \varphi(x, \xi_k) (iz)^l \right\} e^{i\xi_k z} + o((\xi - \xi_k)^{m_k-1}).$$

Unda ($\operatorname{res}_{z=z_0} f(z) = c_{-1}$ bo‘lgani uchun)

$$R \equiv \operatorname{res}_{\xi=\xi_k} \{\varphi(x, \xi) S_{11}(\xi) e^{i\xi z}\} = \sum_{j=0}^{m_k-1} \left\{ \sum_{l=0}^j \frac{(iz)^l}{l!(j-l)!} \varphi(x, \xi_k) S_{j+1}^{(k)} \right\} e^{i\xi_k z}$$

bo‘ladi. Buni (3) tengliklardan foydalanib

$$R \equiv \sum_{j=0}^{m_k-1} \left\{ \sum_{l=0}^j \frac{(iz)^l}{l!(j-l)!} \psi(x, \xi_k) R_{j+1}^{(k)} \right\} e^{i\xi_k z} = \sum_{j=0}^{m_k-1} \frac{(iz)^j}{j!} \left\{ \sum_{l=j}^{m_k-1} \frac{1}{(j-l)!} \psi(x, \xi_k) R_{j+1}^{(k)} \right\} e^{i\xi_k z}$$

(8)

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ko‘rinishda yozish mumkin.

Agar oxirgi tenglikda $\psi(x, \xi) = e^{i\xi x}$ desak, u holda

$$\sum_{j=0}^{m_k-1} \frac{(iz)^l}{l!} \left\{ \sum_{j=l}^{m_k-1} \frac{(ix)^{j-l}}{(j-l)!} R_{j+1}^{(k)} e^{i\xi_n(z+x)} \right\} = \sum_{j=0}^{m_k-1} \frac{1}{j!} R_{j+1} \left\{ \sum_{l=0}^j C_j^l (iz)^l (ix)^{j-l} \right\} e^{i\xi_n(z+x)} =$$

$$= \sum_{j=0}^{m_k-1} \frac{R_{j+1}}{j!} (i(z+x))^j e^{i\xi_n(z+x)}.$$

tenglikni xosil qilamiz.

Agar $R_k(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{m_k-1} \frac{(ix)^j}{j!} R_{j+1} e^{i\xi_n x}$ belgilash kiritsak, u holda

$$\psi(x, \xi) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\xi x} + \int_x^\infty K(x, t) e^{i\xi t} dt \quad \text{ga Levin tasvirini qo‘yib}$$

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} R_k(x+z) + \int_x^\infty K(x, s) R_k(s+z) ds$$

tenglikni xosil qilamiz.

(4) tenglikning chap tarafini integrallagandan keyin

$$i \sum_{k=1}^N \left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} R_k(x+z) + \int_x^\infty K(x, s) R_k(s+z) ds \right)$$

ko‘rinishga keladi. Ushbu $F_k(x) = -i \sum_{j=l}^{m_k-1} \frac{(ix)^{j-l}}{(j-l)!} R_{j+1}^{(k)} e^{i\xi_n x}$ va

$$F(x) = \sum_{k=1}^N F_k(x) + F_s(x) \quad (9)$$

belgilashlar kiritsak quyidagi

$$\bar{K}(x, z) + \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} F(x+z) + \int_x^\infty K(x, s) F(s+z) ds = 0$$

integral tenglama kelib chiqadi. Buni

$$\begin{cases} K_2(x, z) + \int_x^\infty K_1(x, s) F(s+z) ds = 0 \\ F(x+z) - K_1(x, z) + \int_x^\infty K_2(x, s) F(s+z) ds = 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

ko‘rinishda ham yozish mumkin.

Xulosa:

ushbu maqolada sochilish nazariyasining berilganlari orqali $u(x)$ potensialni

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topish, shu bilan birga sochilish nazariyasining berilganlari orqali $u(x)$ potensialni topish imkonini beradigan asosiy integral tenglama keltirilgan

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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